

PROMOTING A WELL-ROUNDED LIFESTYLE FOR SCHOOL KIDS AND COLLEGE STUDENTS

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***Annotation:** This article attempts to reveal the main reasons for the role of attitudes towards healthy lifestyles among high school students and university graduate students. To carry out scientific work, the author used the methods of questionnaire survey, analytical, logical and statistical. The primary material was obtained using the method of questionnaire survey, in which 30 high school students and 36 students of the Medical University were involved. To substantiate the conclusions in the descriptive statistics of the study results, relative percentages were used. The problem in question is still little studied, therefore, requires more thorough research.*

Key words: *Public health, Formation of a healthy lifestyle (HLS), students.*

Introduction: Public health is the study and development of strategic and tactical organizational, medical and social proposals aimed at protecting and improving the level of public health and the quality of medical care.

By the nature of its activity, public health is the study of the healing effect, as well as the adverse impact of social factors and conditions on the health of the population and its groups, and the development of scientifically based recommendations for the elimination and prevention of the influence of social conditions and factors harmful to human health in the interests of protecting and improving level of public health. (Great Medical Encyclopedia (BME. 3rd ed. - T. 25. - P. 60).

The object of public health research is: users of services of medical institutions, health care institutions, medical personnel, regulations and others.

Public health and healthcare (also public health) is a branch of medicine that studies the public health system and healthcare organizations, as well as social (public) health problems. This is the theoretical foundation of healthcare.

The health of young people today is of great interest, because the health of the nation subsequently depends on the state of this category of the population. The formation of a healthy lifestyle (HLS) for students is a complex task, in the implementation of which, of course, educational organizations play the main role. However, as practice shows, few people think about the health of students during intensive classroom studies. Scheduled breaks from 10 to 60 minutes, provided for the restoration of students' working capacity, are used by the latter more often incorrectly, without benefit to their health. The knowledge about healthy lifestyles acquired at school does not find practical application within the walls of the university, and this mission assigned to the system of vocational education, according to experts, is not being fulfilled.

Aim: To study the attitude towards healthy lifestyles of high school students and university graduate students.

Materials and Methods: To achieve the aim of the study, the methods of questionnaire survey, analytical, logical and statistical were used. The primary material was obtained using the method of questionnaire survey, in which 30 high school students and 36 students of the Medical University were involved. To substantiate the conclusions in the descriptive statistics of the study results, relative percentages were used.

Results: According to a questionnaire survey, the majority of schoolchildren (53.3%) and students (33.3%) feel tired at the end of all classes, while the proportion of people who come to class already tired is higher - 16.7% compared to 3% of students. It was found that almost a quarter of school students (26.7%) do not know how to cope with stress, but want to learn it. For students, smoking during breaks is a habit in 13.9% of cases, while for 25% of schoolchildren it is a way of making new acquaintances. In their free time between classes, the majority of schoolchildren and students prefer to eat: 46.7% and 55.6%, respectively. According to high school students, a healthy lifestyle contributes more to success in life (30%), overshadowing its influence on attractiveness (23.3%) and good mood (10%). The results obtained in this study coincide with the materials of sociological surveys of students presented by S.A. Strizhov (2009), according to which a healthy lifestyle improves health (80.6%), supports working capacity (60.8%), provides a good mood (53%), maintains attractiveness (46.7%), and contributes to success in life and business (45.5%) [5].

Conclusions: Given the importance of a healthy lifestyle for young people and the available reserves for its improvement, this work must be purposefully carried out in all educational organizations.

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